

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

Prediction of Adverse Effects Following Radiotherapy: Genome and Transcriptome Analysis

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13987743

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Due to the use of modern therapeutic approaches, survival rates of localized prostate cancer (PCa) patients fortunately increased over the past decade resulting in over 98% of 5-year survival rates. Nearly half of Pca patients will receive radiotherapy (RT), and a significant proportion of them have a chance to develop adverse effects. Firstly, the studies investigating molecular background of radiotoxicity were predominantly based on genomic analysis. The results from previous Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have shown that the presence of some polymorphic regions of particular genes may be associated with the incidence of radiotherapy adverse effects. Recently, radiation oncologists and molecular biologists are investigating molecular basis constructing the backbone of signaling pathways and molecular mechanisms resulting in different grades of side effects following RT by sequencing whole transcriptome and miRNome to set the basis for the prediction of individual patient's sensitivity. This could be starting point toward changes in treatment modalities and clinical study design. Nevertheless, there are some challenges and questions to address before starting RNA-seq analysis such as setting the adequate protocol for RNA extraction, and the protocol for RNA-seq library preparation, as well as to establish the workflow for RNA library preparation, RNA fragmentation, ligation of adapters, reverse transcription and PCR, and how to choose the sequencing method and platform. Sequentially, after the experimental work, it is important to establish the pipeline for raw data processing, choose adequate tools and software for sequence alignment, assembly of transcripts, differential gene expression analysis, visualization, and gene set enrichment analysis.

Keywords: RNA sequencing, MicroRNA, Radiotherapy, Prostate Cancer

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193